

THE EFFECT OF JOB SATISFACTION ON TEACHERS' CREATIVITY IN USING SUPPLEMENTARY EQUIPMENT IN LEARNING ENGLISH IN IRANIAN ENGLISH INSTITUTES

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Abstract:

Teachers' job satisfaction and creativity in the teaching process are very important to the continuous growth of educational systems around the world. Satisfaction and creation at work are very essential in teachers' life because they form the fundamental reasons to vitalize the teaching and learning atmosphere. This study was carried out to probe into a kind of precise research to investigate the effect of job satisfaction on teachers' creativity in using side equipment among EFL teachers in English institutes. To this end, 50 teachers who were teaching EFL at "Adib", "Alborz" and "Rouyesh No" English Institutes in Rasht, Iran were selected. They were selected based on their job experiences and their availabilities. Their English teaching experience varied from 5 to 20 years. Their ages ranged from 20 to 50 years. They were invited to fill out a researcher-developed questionnaire. It was a questionnaire which included 20 items and there were two parts. The first part of the questionnaire asked about job satisfaction among the teachers, and the second part asked about their creative use of side equipment in classroom. The findings suggested that the teachers hold different views regarding job satisfaction and teachers with high level of job satisfaction are more creative in using side equipment. Besides, job satisfaction increases creativity in using equipment in EFL classrooms. Furthermore, if the teachers are satisfied with their job, they develop and maintain a high level of performance and learning process would be more efficient and effective.

Keywords: creativity, creative teaching, creative thinking, equipment, job satisfaction

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1. Introduction

Job is not only a main source of income, but also an important component of life and takes away a large part of each worker's day. Because of the work's central role in many peoples' life, satisfaction with one's job is an important component in overall wellbeing (Smith, 2007). Education is an essential component of human society. Most experts and scholars of educational issues believe that teachers are the biggest and most important factor in education. So it is not surprising to be said that teachers are the base of a successful educational system. The first step toward a successful teaching staff is understanding the factors that affect the quality of teachers. Therefore, the issue of job satisfaction of teachers needs more attention because of its direct relation to their functions. Teachers with more job satisfaction may do the best. So it is necessary to consider the teachers' job satisfaction more than before. Accordingly, a teacher, who is happy with her/ his job, plays a pivotal role in the uplift of the students in particular and society as a whole.

The employees of every job could be creative (Bhatt, 2001). So the organizational researchers must determine variables that caused to the encouragement of creativity so that the organizations can enjoy the creativity and the managers must know how to support these creativities (Duffy, 2000). Among different organizations, institutional organizations, especially educational system has an important role in human life. The creative people in the educational system and other scientific centers are as a must because these centers play an important role to teach the committed and expert human resources for all organizations and departments. Having a creative teacher can create a fundamental change in the educational system. Undoubtedly creativity of teachers is a vital phenomenon among schools and institutions.

This study is important because it assesses the present conditions of the teachers in different English language institutes in terms of satisfaction and creativity Iran. The Department of Education may use the data as basis for policy-making and program planning for institution which promotes creativity in using side equipment in the class and job satisfaction of teachers and professional growth of administrators towards better education. The results may further help the institution administrators to review existing motivational policies and practices with a hope that they can enhance work creatively and job satisfaction among the teachers. This has been the basis to plan programs for teacher development that leads to the teacher's professional growth. It also helps them identify specific demographic characteristics of the teachers which could influence work creatively and job satisfaction of teachers. Finally, this study seems to be very important because it awakens the teachers to conduct periodic self-assessment to improve their teaching creativity. Consequently, to help Iranian EFL teachers' improving creativity in using side equipment in order to facilitate the process of teaching and learning, this study tries to examine the effectiveness of teachers' job satisfaction which is undoubtedly necessary for their creation.

Despite the significant role and effect of job satisfaction on classes a paucity of research has been conducted to seek the effect of job satisfaction on teachers' creativity in English classrooms. The overall objective of this study is to examine the level of job satisfaction with English teachers in English institutions and to find out the effect of job satisfaction on their creativity in using extracurricular equipment in English classes. It is hoped that this study would help language institute to have more creative and satisfied teachers.

To fulfill the aims this study sought to answer the following questions:

RQ1: Is there any statistically significant correlation between teachers' creativity in using inside equipment and their job satisfaction?

RQ2: Does job satisfaction have any statistically significant impact on teachers' creativity in using side equipment in Iranian language institute?

2. Literature Review

Despite its wide usage in scientific research, as well as in everyday life, there is still no general agreement regarding what job satisfaction is. Therefore, before a definition of job satisfaction can be given, the nature and importance of work as a universal human activity must be considered. Job satisfaction is a worker's sense of achievement and success on the job. It is generally perceived to be directly linked to productivity as well as to personal well-being. Job satisfaction implies doing a job one enjoys, doing it well and being rewarded for one's efforts. Job satisfaction further implies enthusiasm and happiness with one's work. It is the key ingredient that leads to recognition, income, promotion, and the achievement of other goals that lead to a feeling of fulfillment (Kaliski, 2007). When analyzing job satisfaction the considerable logic is that a satisfied employee is a happy employee and a happy employee is a successful employee. Teachers' job satisfaction and creativity are very important to the continuous growth of educational systems around the world. Almost every teacher works in order to satisfy their needs, deficiency and growth.

Beshruyehgi and Aslizadeh (2014) investigated the impact of job satisfaction on organizational creativity through practical, descriptive-survey based and quantitative (using questionnaires) study. The research population included the Dey insurance company's staff, that is, 600 persons, and 384 of them are chosen for the research using Cochran formula. The results presented a significant and positive impact of job satisfaction and its dimensions (nature of work, leader's features, partner's features, promotion, and salary and wage) on staff creativity.

In another study Hasani (2010) investigated the intermediating role of job satisfaction on the empowerment, creativity and innovation in Education department in West Azarbayejan province. It was found there are significant relations between creativity and innovation and also the job satisfaction can anticipate the creativity and innovation. Ebrahimi (2015) designed the survey to investigate the relationship between different factors and English teachers' job satisfaction in Iranian English as a Foreign Language (EFL). In so doing, a sample of 80 EFL teachers, who was teaching English in

English language institutes in Tehran, Iran was selected. The participants' views towards their job and other factors were investigated using three Likert-type questionnaires. The results of descriptive statistics revealed that Iranian EFL teachers were not satisfied with school-based and system-based factors of their career.

3. Methods

3.1. Design

This study used a descriptive survey design. The purpose of descriptive surveys, according to Ezeani (1998) is to collect detailed and factual information that describes an existing phenomenon. The level of job satisfaction and creativity in using side equipment in EFL classes was analyzed by distributing questionnaires. A researcher-designed questionnaire was developed including items asking the teachers about their job satisfaction as well as their creativity in using side equipment. The reliability and the validity of the questionnaire were examined through a pilot study. The participants of the study were selected from population members who were conveniently available to participate in study. The questionnaires were distributed by the researchers among the teachers. The needed data for the study were collected through a questionnaire. The qualitative analysis of the data was conducted and the results were summarized. The Quantitative analysis of the data was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

3.2. Participants

The participants were 50 foreign language teachers who were teaching in Adib and Alborz Institutes, Shokouh Institute, Rouyeshe No Institute, and some other institutions that were chosen for participation in this study. They were all from Rasht and Persian was their first language. Participants were both males and females. Their English teaching experience varied from 5 to 20 years. The ages of the teachers ranged between 20 and 50 years. The sample who participated in the study included trained and educated teachers working in the elementary and advanced level. These EFL teachers were invited to respond to the questionnaires.

3.3. Instrument

Like other investigation, some materials were used in this study to lead better and more comprehensive findings. The research design used for the study is a survey which necessitated the use of a questionnaire in gathering data for the study. So a questionnaire was developed by the researchers and it was utilized to obtain the data for this study. When choosing an appropriate research instrument, validity and reliability are important factors to consider. Reliability and validity of the research instrument were established through the pilot study. The main research instrument used in the study was the questionnaire. It was a researcher-developed questionnaire included 20 items and there were two parts. The first part of the questionnaire asked about job satisfaction among the teachers, the second part asked about the creativity

and innovation of the teachers in using side equipment in English class. by the researchers in order to measure and analyze: firstly the effectiveness of the teachers' job satisfaction on their creativity, secondly to estimate that to what extent satisfied and dissatisfied teachers are eager for using side equipment in the extracurricular programs.

3.4. Data Collection Procedures

Prior to the collection of the data, the teachers were informed about the study and their consent was obtained. Then the questionnaires were distributed among the teachers and the needed data were collected. They were required to select a choice, which best fitted their choice in their view. Descriptive analyses were performed on the teachers' responses to the questionnaire.

3.5. Data Analysis

This study utilized survey method. The essence of survey method can be explained as questioning individuals on a topic or topics and then describing their responses. In studies survey method of primary data collection is used in order to test concepts, reflect attitude of people, establish the level of teachers' satisfaction, and conduct segmentation research and a set of other purposes. Survey method can be used in both, quantitative, as well as, qualitative studies.

4. Results and Discussion

The results were presented in accordance with the research questions of the study. The parametric statistical analyses were run to probe the mentioned null-hypothesis. The statistical technique assumed normality of the data and homogeneity of the participants of the groups. The statistical technique assumed normality of the data and homogeneity of the participants of the groups. The research can be divided into two sections to answer the research questions.

A. Research Question One

One of the very important assumptions for running correlational procedures is having normal distribution. As indicated, both tests of Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk report the normal distribution within the intended variables (job satisfaction and creativity). Test of normality is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Test of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Job satisfaction	.109	50	.192	.960	50	.087
Creativity	.118	50	.078	.974	50	.342

Test of linear relationship between the variables is the other necessary assumption for running correlational procedures, illustrated in the figure below. The scatterplots

clearly show that the variable of the current study have linear relationships; so, any non-linear relationships are ruled out. Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation test's output are also presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Creativity	3.8000	.53558	50
Job satisfaction	3.9728	.10044	50

Table 3: Output from Pearson Correlation Test

		Creativity	Job satisfaction
Creativity	Pearson Correlation	1	.493 ^a
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	50	50
Job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.493 ^a	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	50	50

a. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A Pearson's correlation between the EFL teachers' job satisfaction and their creativity found that the effect size of the correlation was moderate (95% CI, $r=.493$, $N=50$, $R^2 = 0.25$) meaning that the correlation coefficient is fairly high and statistically significant. In other words, creativity and job satisfaction with language teachers are positively and significantly correlated. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. Table 4 presents the regression output.

B. Research Question Two

Table 4: Regression Output: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.493 ^a	.243	.228	.47069	.243	15.443	1	48	.000	1.825

a. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

b. Dependent Variable: creativity

The model clearly represents that the independent variable, job satisfaction in this study, can predict approximately 25% of variances of the EFL teachers' creativity, while the rest is determined by other factors which have not been included in the present research. The results of ANOVA are illustrated in Table 5.

Table 5: ANOVA result^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.421	1	3.421	15.443	.000 ^a
	Residual	10.634	48	.222		
	Total	14.056	49			

a. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

b. Dependent Variable: creativity

Moving on to the next part of the output, Table 5 shows the results of an ANOVA performed on the model. The ANOVA tests the null hypothesis that the predictive power of the model is equal to zero. The findings indicate that the regression analysis is significant. Table 6 is the coefficient output table which shows a significant piece of output, giving explanatory information about the equation. VIF reported in the table represents that there is no multicollinearity in the explanatory variables.

Table 6: Coefficient^a Output

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
		1	(Constant)	1.293			.389		3.323	.002
	Job satisfaction	2.631	.669	.493	3.930	.000	1.285	3.977	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: creativity

According to the table, the model would predict that the score in creativity could be modeled by:

$$Y = 2.631 * \text{job satisfaction} + 1.293 \quad (1)$$

The findings are in line with Dugguh, and Dennis (2014) in that job satisfaction plays a crucial role in terms of employee performance, and to some extent his well-being and to the organizations in terms of its productivity, efficiency, employee relations, absenteeism and turnover. Since job satisfaction is a complex variable, it can be influenced by situational factors on the job as well as the dispositional characteristics of the individual. Research examining relationships between job satisfaction and employee satisfaction and the methodologies utilized has great variations. These methodologies range from established scales, self-report ratings to peer or supervisor ratings

The study is also in line with some research that show creative people regard their future goals and perspectives of their job in order to achieve success and through career path planning should define, measure and manage their type and value of human resources toward gaining goals by coordinating them (Salmanpour, 2012). So in this way, creativity may lead people to be more satisfied with their job. It also refers to teachers, some studies have dealt with the issues of teachers' creativity and their job satisfaction separately; in most of them, the relationship between these two issues have been mentioned and investigated specially about teachers who are working in schools and those who are active in institutes.

In fact, although a lot of scholars like Ebrahimi (2015) found that teachers' dissatisfaction with their jobs may be mainly due to the insufficient salary, and/or due to the fact that the educational system does not give appropriate values to different teaching qualities, their findings were not in agreement with the present study. This study not only investigated different factors that can influence job satisfaction of language instructors but also tried to examine how teachers' job satisfaction affects their creativity in using side equipment.

5. Conclusion

The results of this study are useful for institute managers. It can be concluded that pedagogy and teacher effectiveness have to be an important determinant for the perception of teaching effectiveness. Therefore, stress free environment should be provided to teachers and they should also be provided with all basic necessities for teaching in the classroom. Continuous reframing of the policies best suited for the teachers and students should be done for effective teaching learning.

As a result of this study, teachers and school administrators are likely to have a better understanding in knowing the importance of teachers' creativity, attitude and commitment. Future research should further explore the same independent variables and its effect on students' performance in other subjects taught in school. Another future research could look at the effects of creativity on public school teachers.

As the results of the study suggested job satisfaction affects teachers' work and life in many aspects. Satisfied teachers are more creative in their classes because their minds are not preoccupied with job related issues. Not need to say that according to the designed questionnaire and according to the answers, job satisfaction includes many

items, first of which is the payment and then the atmosphere, etc. Hence to have satisfied teachers, one should consider many items.

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